

LINGUISTIC SCHEMA: A CATALYST FOR IMPROVING JSS TWO STUDENTS
PERFORMANCE IN READING FOR LITERAL COMPREHENSION IN ZARIA
METROPOLIS

DÀ AND *NKÓ*: A PREDICATIVE VIEW

BY

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Abstract

In furtherance of the arguments advanced in Taiwo and Abimbola (2014) on “dà” and “ńkó”, classified traditionally as verbs in Yorùbá grammar, this paper argues that “dà” and “ńkó” are verbs against Awobuluyi’s (2013) and Olaogun and Asiwaju (2016) submissions. In Awobuluyi (2013), “dà” and “ńkó” are viewed as a non-verbal items based on certain co-occurrence restriction imposed on them by Yorùbá short pronouns on the one hand. On the other hand, “dà” and “ńkó” are said to share some similarities with certain functors like the focus marker among others. The two items were classified as wh-words by Olaogun and Asiwaju (2016). In this article however, eight arguments are advanced in favour of predicative reading of “dà” and “ńkó” to further show that non-predicative interpretation of the two items is misleading. The properties shows that “dà” and “ńkó” are verbs in Yorùbá and that Awobuluyi’s claim does not nullify them as verbs in clauses where they are used. It concludes that every lexical item has it peculiarities with which one may identify it as a member of a larger category, and may narrowly have some features which will set such apart from all the members of that category.

Keywords: “dà” and “ńkó”, predicative, non-predicative, verbs, Yorùbá.

INTRODUCTION

Lexical items may be classified based on specific syntactic features defining a set of items as a class. Within a given class as well, it is not unlikely to see certain items with specific different features as opposed to general features for characterizing all the members as a class. And having a specific syntactic feature to the exclusion of others in the class does not limit such item's functionality within the clause. This observation is evident in the following examples;

- 1a. John *said* that Kim will be here soon. 1b. John *blocked* the ridge.
1c. He *asked* if Kim knew the man.

The italicized words in (1a-c) are verbs. These verbs have transitivity feature as shared commonality but have different peculiarities distinguishing them. And, the fact that 'said', 'blocked' and 'asked' have individual features excluding others do not undermine being included in the class of 'transitive' verbs. In the same vein, traditional Yoruba grammarians have a class of verb often denoted as interrogative or question verb because verbs classified in this class are primarily used for asking questions. There are two types in standard Yoruba while there are different correlates in Yoruba dialects. This class reflects an aspect of Yoruba native speakers' understanding of the way words are assigned meanings, functions or usage in actual sentences of the language. And it is the basic concern of linguists to describe the native speakers' implicit knowledge of his language. However, whenever such description is contentious, careful investigations to establish the truth must be carried out. Hence, a native speaker knows when he is communicating and when his utterances are rendered in error. Similarly, Yoruba language speakers know that the following are acceptable sentences in the language:

- | | | |
|----------------------------|---------------------|-------------------------|
| 2a) Olá ra òkò tuntun | b) Ọkò náà dà? | c) Ọkò náà ñkó báyii? |
| Ola buy-NF car new | Car Def. QV | car Def. QV like this |
| “Ola bought a new car” | “Where is the car?” | “where is the car now?” |

Yoruba language speakers know that there is a difference in the way (2a) is used and structured as opposed to the way (2b) and (2c) are used and structured. A lot has been said by Yoruba scholars on the 'verbalness' of *dà* and *ńkó*. Scholars like Abraham (1958), Awobuluyi (1978, 2008, and 2013), Bamgbose (1990), Taiwo and Abimbola (2014), Akanbi (2014) have said one thing or the other on these lexical items. Speakers would adjudge (2b) and (2c) as sentences, specifically as interrogative sentences. This view shall be referred to as predicative view. Other view, referred to as non-predicative view in this paper, assumes that *dà* and *ńkó* in (2b) and (2c) above are not verbs based on their inability to co-occur with short pronouns while other predicative features are neglected (cf. Awobuluyi, 2013). By implication, sentences (2b) and (2c) are not sentences and they do not have any predicative element. Hence, the present paper is primarily concerned with sentences like (2b) and (2c) by investigating with the aim of establishing the predicative features of the two items. Extant works' views were identified and critiqued and attention is given to Awobuluyi (2013) non-predicative argument whose definition of verb in the language narrows down to only the items that can co-occur with short pronouns. After this, evidence will be advanced to further the claim that *dà* and *ńkó* are verbs in the language.

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Previous views on *dà* and *ńkọ*

As far as the present writer knows, *dà* (and *ńkọ*) was first mentioned in Abraham (1958:121) dictionary. He noted that, “*Dà* “where is”? (the tone of the subject of this word does not rise, showing that this is not a true verb: v Tone rule) \underline{x} àjẹ *dà* where is the paddle? Òun *dà* = òun ha *dà* = níbo ló *dà* where is he? (not òun *dà*) = *ń-kọ* 1 (v ibo).” This remark points to the nature of the item; thus, making it a suspect among verbs. Abraham’s view belongs to the class of non-predicative view of *dà* and *ńkọ*. However, he did not actually say that *dà* and *ńkọ* are not verbs. Consider the following;

3a) *Olú dà/ńkọ*

Olu QV

where is *Olu*?”

b) *Akin dà/ńkọ*

Akin QV

“where is *Akin*/what about *Akin*?”

c) *Akín ra bàtà*

Akin buy:NF shoe

“*Akin* bought a pair of shoe”

d) [*Bàtà [tí Akín rà] dà/ńkọ*]

[shoe [*RelM Akin buy:NF QV*]

“where is the shoe that *Akin* bought?”

Notice that on *Olú* which has high tone on its last syllable does not manifest tone raising on the subject as observed by Abraham in (3a). The same is true of *Akin* (3b), a mid-tone nominal subject on its last syllable. But in (3c) and (3d), the tone on *Akin*’s last syllable was raised. This raising was by no means triggered by the verb. It resulted from the merger *Akin* + *ó* = *Akín*, (cf. Awobuluyi, 1992 and other works). It should be noted however, that the event coded by the expressions in (2a-d) above are not in non-future. There are vast literatures available on the High Tone Syllable (HTS). Ogbeifun and Abimbola (2020) and Awobuluyi (2019) have suggested that \acute{o} denotes non-future tense in *Úsẹn* and Standard Yoruba respectively. This being the case, the cases expressed in (3a-d) above are in the time “now to infinity” when the actions will be completed and perfected, that is, point present to future infinity¹. Hence, there is nothing to trigger the presence of high tone 1 from non-high. This suffices to say that the verbs are not responsible for high tone raising on the last syllable of the subject noun/nominal. By implication, the inability of a non-high resulting to a high tone in certain environments does not limit the ability of *dà* and *ńkọ* as verbs in Yoruba.

Awobuluyi (1978) listed *dà* and *ńkọ* under a class of verb called ‘interrogative verb’. Invariably, he believes that *dà* and *ńkọ* are verbs because these two items predicate the clauses where they are used. Not only did

¹ cf. Bull (1963) and Omamor (1982) among others.

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- 9a) Ìwé *dà/ńkọ* 9b) Iṣé wà yàtò sí *Iṣé wà ǹnkankan
9c) Owó *dà* yàtò sí *owó da ǹnkankan

Since *dà* and *ńkọ* are not transitive, exchanging object positions occupied by *iwà* and *èniyàn* in (10a-b) below is not a possible, (cf. Bamgbose, 1990:136-137).

- | | |
|--|-------------------------|
| 10a) Wọ̀n yí iwà padà | b) Adé bẹ̀rù èniyàn |
| They turn behaviour back | Ade fear people |
| “they changed (their) behaviour” | “Ade feared the people” |

Unlike the verbs *yí...padà* and *bẹ̀rù*, *dà* (and *ńkọ*) cannot select object nouns or noun phrases. It has no cognate object like *lá* as in (11) where *àlá kan* is the object of *lá* as the only possible object that verb. On the tone rule which he alluded to, the tone on the item cannot rise because it is simply intransitive and cannot be so used transitively. It cannot behave as other transitive monosyllabic verbs in the language that changes a low tone to high before nominal object complement as shown in (12) below.

- | | | |
|---------------------|--|--|
| 11) Mo lá àlá kan | 12a) Rà: bàbà ra ẹ̀ran “Baba bought a ram” | |
| 1sg dream dream one | b) Gbìn: àgbẹ̀ gbìn ata “the framer planted pepper” | |
| “I had a dream” | c) Jà: wọ̀n jà ní gbangba “they fought in the open” | |

Notice that all the three verbs used above are monosyllabic low tone verbs. Tone change rule between the low tone verb and the object noun/noun phrases is noticeable between *rà* “buy” and *ẹ̀ran* “meat”, the object of the verb in (12a) and the same is true between *gbìn* “plant” and its object *ata* “pepper” its object complement in (12b) on the one hand. On the other hand, *jà* a low tone monosyllabic verb in (12c) does not induce such a change because it is not a transitive verb. Apart from this, the *dà* mentioned in “*níbo ló dà*” does not seem to have the same interpretation with the *dà* under discussion. That one seems to have a variant *dì*.

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|-------------------------|
| 13a) Ó <i>dì</i> èyìn oṣù m̀erìn | b) Ó <i>dì</i> ìgbà–wò? |
| HTS become back month four | HTS become period-which |
| “till after four month” | “till when?” |

In essence, the fact that the tone on *dà* does not change has not changed its status nor make it a suspect. Whenever low tone monosyllabic transitive verbs and monosyllabic intransitive verbs in Yoruba take prepositional phrase complement, the tone will not change.

Akanbi (2014) also noted that *dà* and *ńkọ* are syntactically and semantically different. Syntactically, *dà* is used to ask questions about “where” while *ńkọ* asks questions about “where” and “how”. Semantically, Akanbi (2014:13) noted that *dà* and *ńkọ* “actually perform similar semantic role in one particular instance but also perform different semantic roles in some other cases”. Also, *dà* may be used sarcastically whereas *ńkọ* cannot be so used. Hence, he claimed that in certain instances *ńkọ* can mean “what about” which *dà* cannot denote.” He noted to *dà* and *ńkọ* as having two different properties: “question words” and “verbs”. This observation aligns with Taiwo and Abimbola (2014) that claims that the two interrogative verbs are verbs and at the same time functions as the question head in interrogative phrases. Akanbi emphasised that *dà* and *ńkọ* can only be used in-situ. That is, the two verbs are not a movement triggering or licensing items. This claim contradicts Taiwo and Abimbola’s (2014) view. They noted that the two verbs raise to the head of interrogative phrase on Head-to-Head adjunction for interrogative interpretation mapping on the clause in the left periphery. Akanbi also noted that *dà* and *ńkọ* require content statement as responses. This may have informed Olaogun and Asiwaju’s (2016) grouping of the item with *kí*, *ta*, *èwo*, among others. Due to the claim that assumes no-movement licensing for the two interrogatives, it was convenient for Akanbi to claim that *dà* and *ńkọ* are not subject to move alpha rule unlike wh-items. Akanbi’s view on the syntactic position of *dà* and *ńkọ* in the clause emphasises that the two items are verbs when he said that the two verbs occupy positions where intransitive verbs are found in the clause. This last point raised by Akanbi supported the claim earlier raised in favour no-argument object licensing raised above. It suffices to say that the two items are verbs contrary to non-predicative view.

Taiwo and Abimbola (2014) have a different in approach to others because their position is taking from a minimalist point of view. Their argument that *dà* and *ńkọ* are verbs based on certain features: a) *dà* and *ńkọ* are intransitive and cannot be used transitively. Any attempt to use the two items transitively would result in non-existent constructions in the language. b) Co-occurrence with PP complement just as unaccusative verbs do. That is, *dà* and *ńkọ* may be followed by a preposition phrase. c) Inability of *dà* and *ńkọ* to co-occur with short pronouns. d) Sentences in which the two interrogative verbs are used are interrogatives and the two verbs are underlyingly marked as interrogatives. e) *Dà* and *ńkọ* are said to occur in complementary distribution with *ta*, *kí*, *èwo*, *èlọ*, among others which are nouns. Hence, they cannot be used the same way. f) Their clausal derivations are not like every other type of constructions. They assume that question feature on *dà* and *ńkọ* is weak. Hence, there is a need for movement of these items to the interrogative head while their subjects move to spec TP according to Ilori (2010) and Oduntan (2000). g) *dà* and *ńkọ* assign theme theta role to their subjects.

They discuss reasons why the *dà* and *ńkọ* cannot be question marker rather they are to be considered as verbs: a) Replacement of argument structure, b) Inclusiveness condition c) Featureless valuation and d) Interfaces issues. These arguments are theoretically motivated.

In Olaogun and Asiwaju (2016) the two items; *dà* and *ńkọ* were called wh-items because *dà* and *ńkọ* are interpreted as “where” in English. This view seems to be too narrow. And it is a wrong prediction of Yoruba native speakers’ intuition. Focus constructions are responses to wh-constructions in the language. As argued above, they cannot be so equated. It should be noted that sometimes languages do not have one-to-one lexical correspondence. Thus, a closely related item would be used to interpret the idea being conveyed. As a corollary to the aforementioned fact relating interrogative verbs with wh-words in the language, *dà* and

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*ńkọ*⁴ never select focus constructions as complement just as wh-questions do. For example, the italicized phrases are focused phrases headed by the focus marker *ni* in the language;

16a) Asín gé e ní imú jẹ b) Asín ni ó gé e ní imú jẹ

Rat bite 2sg prep nouse eat Rat Foc 2sg bite Obj. prep nouse eat

‘The rat bit him/her on his/her nouse’ ‘It was the rat that bit him/her on the nouse’

c) Kí ni Olú fẹ se

what Foc Olu want do

“what does Olu want to do”

17a) Nígba wo ni Fọlá fẹ padà sí Gánà? b) Ta ni a ó rán ní ojà náà?

Which time Foc Fola want return prep Ghana who Foc 1pl HTS send prep market

“when will Fola return to Ghana?”

“Who shall we send to the market?”

In Yoruba, wh-items are usually displaced from clause-internal position to clause left periphery in the specifier of the interrogative clause/constructions. That is, Yoruba wh-items like *kí*, *ta*, *èwo*, etc, do not occupy head of InterP (interrogative phrase construction) because they are not the question marker but the item representing what is questioned in the clause⁵. *Dà* and *ńkọ* do not occupy the spec- InterP cartographically as evident in the fact that an item is selected for question force marking in the same clause containing *dà* and *ńkọ*.

In standard Yoruba, and Kwa languages in general, the focus marker and question marker are said to compete for the same structure position⁶. Hence, focus articulation being the first articulated projection weeds out the overt realization of wh-interrogative marker. In furtherance of the already established differences between wh-items and *dà* and *ńkọ*, the following are to be noted in the behaviours of wh-items in the Yoruba. That is *kí*, *ta*, *èwo*, etc are; (a) not functional words and not head of their projections; (b)

⁴ And by implication *síkọ*, the form of interrogative verb in central Yoruba dialects does not have focus construction as complement. e.g. Olú síkọ?

⁵ See Abimbola (2019) for a detailed discussion on distinguishing questioned items or the information the speaker seeks to know from the addressee and the question marker.

⁶ See Aboh (2007) for detail discussion, and Abimbola (2019a) for more on ‘questioned item’ and ‘question marker’.

trigger movement of constituents and create gaps through movement chains formed during fronting processes of the wh-items to the left periphery, (c) require overt focus licensing, (d) licensers of A-bar movement type, (e) interpreted with nominal binding rules, co-indexation, identical/identity reference. Contrary to Olaogun and Asiwaju's claim, the argument above suffices to say that *dà* and *ńkọ* do not occupy the same positions as their wh-counterparts in Yoruba and they should not be equated. Awobuluyi (2013: 128) identifies features of verbs in Yoruba based on a number of tests and one of the features establishes *dà* and *ńkọ* as non-predicative items. These tests are discussed below;

- i. Coordination test is used for determining if an item is a constituent. That is, items that can be coordinated are constituents. In other words, if two items cannot be coordinated, then they are not constituents. The requirement of this test is that coordinated constituents (phrases, clauses and sentences) must be the same or equal in unit of grammatical description or must be in the same category syntactically. For examples:

18a) *Ade àti bàbá rẹ lọ sí ilú-òkè.* b) *Bàbá àgbà àti Ààrẹ jẹ ọrẹ tímótímó.*

Ade conj father his go prep town-up baba elder conj president be friend close

“Ade and his father went to the village “the older man and the president are close friends”

c) *Èmi pẹ̀lú rẹ̀ ni a ó ẹ̀ ẹ̀ náà.*

1sgE conj him Foc 1pl HTS do work Def.

“I, and him will do the job”

The italicized phrases in the examples (18a-c) above are nominal items coordinated together with the use of “àti” and “pẹ̀lú” which are nominal conjunctions. Yoruba has a limited number of conjunctions. Most conjunctions can be used with nouns and noun phrases as exemplified above. Similarly, sentences can be coordinated as shown in examples (19a-d).

19a) [_{S1} Wón jà] sùgbón [_{S2} wón ò kú] b) [_{S1} Mo ra aṣọ tuntun] àmó [_{S1} n ò mú un dání]

[They fought] but [they did not die] [I bought a new cloth] but [I did not come with it]

c) [_{S1} wón dī ìbò], [_{S1} wón sì borí] d) [_{S1} ọbọ ọba gé Bàbá jẹ], sùgbón [_{S1} Bàbá ò kú]

[they voted], they worn]

[the king's monkey bit the man] but [the man did

not die]

However, certain types of pronouns may not be used in the same way as the nouns of this language. Nouns can function anaphorically in Yoruba but verbs cannot be so used⁷.

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20) Mo rí *iṣu méje*; mo jẹ *méjì* níbè.

1sg see yam seven; 1sg eat two there

I saw seven yams, I ate two out of it”

21a) *lọ àti jó* yẹn ò dára b) òkanùn ni *pẹlẹja* àti *pa ẹlẹja* ní ìtumò.

‘Go’ conj ‘dance’ that neg good

same Foc *pẹlẹja* conj *pa ẹlẹja* prep meaning

“the ‘go’ and ‘dance’ you wrote are not good”

“both *pẹlẹja* and *pa ẹlẹja* are the same”

Verbs and VPs cannot be coordinated with the use of conjunctions in Yoruba in the same way nominal constituents are conjoined. If they are so used, then such verbs would turn to nouns functionally. Hence, the italicized verbs/verb phrases in (21a-b) are not acceptable as verb rather they are interpreted as nouns. Therefore being nouns functionally, they can be conjoined with nominal conjunctions in the language.

ii. (*verbal*) *Constituent Ellipsis*: yet having grammatical sentences. According to Awobuluyi, only two types of verbs may partially undergo ellipsis in the clause. The first is *jẹ* which after been elided will be replaced by *ni* the focus marker. The second verb is *ṣe* which also has the meaning of *jẹ*. He illustrated with the following example:

22) Ògá ni mo jẹ níbè → Ògá ni níbè.

Master Foc 1sg be there

master Foc there

First, it is pertinent to note that not all verbs in the language may be so used like this. The fact that a non-predicative item replaces a predicate is rather mind-troubling. It thus seems that this claim draws back Yoruba studies to square one where the focus marker was considered as type of verb. Secondly, this process is only possible within focus constructions/structures because focus ‘acts’ in such constructions⁸ as claimed by Awobuluyi (2013). Thirdly, a careful observation of the examples cited by Awobuluyi shows that it is not just the verb that undergoes ellipsis in (22) but a combination of the subject and the verb⁹. The English

⁷ See Abimbola (2019b). This observation has also noted in Awobuluyi (2020).

⁸ Cf. Yusuf (1992). Yusuf is one of those who see the focus marker in Yoruba as a copula verb. However, there are several indications pointing to a fact about language behaviour in examples like this. Language may have identical words seemingly occurring in similar environment. But whenever such are examined, one would observe that the items are functionally different. Interested readers may see Yusuf (1992) and some other researchers who share the view.

example used by Awobuluyi (2013:132) still requires the subject for acceptability and grammaticality and so does the Yoruba example.

23a) John bought oranges and Jane bought bananas. →

23b) John bought oranges and john _ bananas. But not

23c) “John bought oranges and ___ ___ bananas”,

as that of Awobuluyi (2013) Yoruba example shows. As far as the present writer knows, no language speaker speaks in such a way. That is, no speaker leaves out all the vital parts of the clause.

iii) Absence of predicate in *dà/nkó*-clauses: Awobuluyi (2013: 172-175) says concerning *dà (nkó)*, not mentioned) that there is no verb in (24).

24) Oyè dà? “Where is Oye?”

What is rather surprising is that speakers understood this expression as sentence as opposed to using a noun or any word. A question which any speaker would ask is what predicates the clause? Also, does the construction have any meaning to the speaker? Do speakers and hearers struggle to understand by asking for further clarifications of the construction as it is the case in ambiguous constructions? If speakers adjudged (24) as acceptable and grammatical in the language, then it is the duty of linguists to describe why (24) is grammatical and acceptable. Apart from that, Awobuluyi noted that verbs may be preceded by pre-verbs, as in Awobuluyi’s term. But a question that anyone would or should ask is; does the language users/speakers adjudged any of these sentences as grammatical and also associate certain lexical items in the clause/sentences as predicators of the sentences?

25a) Olú dà?

c) Ìwé tí mo rà dà?

Olu QV

Book that 1sg buy QV

“Where is Olu?”

“where is the book that I bought?”

b) Aṣọ tuntun nàà dà bá yí nínú gbogbo ẹ̀rù yí?

⁹ By implication, it is possible that every other thing that intervenes between the subject of the clause and the verb would undergo ellipsis in this type of construction being referred to. For example; (1a) and (1b) below are possible constructions in the language and the two are adjudged grammatical. But (1c) is rather ungrammatical and no speaker speaks like that. Hence, (1c) is not acceptable. But after the ellipsis, (1d) would still be the form produced after the ellipsis. If this be the case, then it is no one can lay claim on such type of ellipsis so referred to in Awobuluyi.

1a) Ọ̀gá kúkú ní mo jẹ̀ nìbẹ̀ 1b) Ọ̀gá ní mo kúkú jẹ̀ nìbẹ̀ 1c) * Ọ̀gá ní kúkú nìbẹ̀ 1d) Ọ̀gá ní nìbẹ̀.
If you compare a non-focused construction like (2a-c) below with those above, it becomes clear that the type of *ní* which are used in such constructions is not the focus marker.

2a) Adé jẹ̀ ọ̀gá akọ̀rín ní ilé ijọ̀sìn wọ̀n. 2b) Adé ní ọ̀gá akọ̀rín ní ilé ijọ̀sìn wọ̀n. 2c) Adé kúkú ní ọ̀gá akọ̀rín ní ilé ijọ̀sìn wọ̀n.

By the reason of kúkú occurring before *ní* shows that that *ní* is not a focus marker.

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Cloth new Def QV like this prep all luggage this

“where is the new cloth in all of these luggage”

Yes! Awobuluyi (1978) had noted under section 4.4 that “Speakers know what verbs are in the language. Although they appear to do so by instinct, the real explanation, in fact, is that, right from infancy, they have learnt to associate a particular place or position in Yoruba sentences with verbs and with verbs only. That position is the one labelled predicator above”. Awobuluyi (1978:43) says that the following expressions are adjudged to be sentences because they contain certain lexical items in solely dedicated predicative positions.

26a) Mo ra iṣu

b) Iná jó ilé

Isg buy yam “I bought yam” fire burn house “fire burned the house”

c) Oba pa àṣẹ

king make command “the king gave an order”

27a) Òjó sùn

b) Ó dára

Ojo sleep “Ojo slept”

_ HTS good “it is good”

c) ó dúdú

d) òun dà

HTS black “it is black

3sgE QV “where is it?”

These examples were given to assert his claim following the definition he gave as “any word functioning as predicator in a grammatical or acceptable sentence in the language is a verb”. And evidently, the verbs select subjects without any contention apart from functioning as predicators in those sentences. He went further to clarify the term *predicator* as “the position between the subject and the object in the following sentences”. Those sentences are stated as (26a-c) and (27a-c) above. The sentences in (26) and (27) above are regarded as simple sentences, while those in 1a-c above are instances of sentences containing subject, verb (i.e. predicator) and object (of the verbs only, sentences (27a-d), however, contain only the subjects and the verbs. They are to be regarded as intransitive sentences. Of all the sentences above, only (27d) is our immediate concern in this work. Awobuluyi (2013) definition of verb considers restrictions imposed

by verb's co-occurrence as the basis for his definition. Fundamentally, three significant words are germane for understanding 30d above: predicator, sentence and grammaticality/acceptability¹⁰.

Awobuluyi (2013:73) notes that the two interrogative items, *dà* and *ńkọ* (and other items listed in the group), may be preceded by preverbal adverbs as the following examples show:

- | | |
|--|---|
| 28a) Ịwọ tiẹ dà. | b) Ịwọ tiẹ kọ ni. |
| “You are not even the one” | “I didn't know that you are not actually the one” |
| c) Ịwọ ọàà kọ ni. | d) Ịwọ tiẹ kúkú kọ ni. |
| “You are not exactly the one” | “I did not know you not even the one” |
| e) Ịwọ mà tiẹ kúkú kọ ni-in. | f) Ịwọ gbọdọ ni (= ịwọ ni ó gbọdọ jẹ/şe) |
| “As a matter of fact, you not even the one” “you must be the one/person” | |

Abstracting away from all the rest of the items in the group, a simple point of interrogating the predicative interpretation of *dà* and *ńkọ* is brought to bear with this question: why can these items be preceded by preverbal adverbs? Awobuluyi said they are a type of verb. It thus seems that there is confusion on how to describe the properties that delimit the two interrogative verbs as verbs. Pre-verbs can only precede verbs. By virtue of these pre-verbs preceding the two interrogative items then they are verbs. A noun, pronoun or any other category may not be preceded by any of these preverbal adverbs. Only verbs, the occurrence of these items is not limited to certain class of verbs, they can occur with other verbs as in,

- | | |
|-----------------|-----------------|
| 29a) Olú tiẹ lọ | b) Olú ọàà jẹun |
|-----------------|-----------------|

¹⁰ Awobuluyi (2013:89), section 3.1.2, has noted that any sentence without a verb is not a sentence. Hence, verb is the most important item in the sentence. But the time (tense) of action or state denoted by the verb is very important as no verb may occur without the time of event. The verb must be coded in time and also be specified as complete or ongoing. Apart from that the force of the clause through which a clause's interpretation as declarative, imperative, interrogative, etc is of essence. Otherwise, the clause will be wrongly interpreted. For instance, no other construction can be termed interrogative if interrogative force is not exerted in the clause. If none of these force interpretations are found in a clause/sentence, then it is not a clause. In the case of *dà* and *ńkọ*, a functional predicative items are found, the sentences are denoted as interrogative and acceptable as meaningful sentences in the language.

In another instance, he claimed that verbs may occur in isolation as sentences (cf. Awobuluyi, 2013: 90). But this usage is restricted to command clauses. Not all verbs may be used in commands. No one would say (a-c) below are acceptable as command sentences in the language. Some must occur with their objects

1a) Jalè! (steal something!) 1b) Jí (to steal) 1c) Kọ (to crow)

It should be noted however, that verbs may not be used without subject (for most verb), tense (for all verbs) and object (for some verbs). If a verb cannot be used with an object, does it mean it is not a verb? *Mo fí sí ibẹ̀*. The *fí* does not have an object, yet it is a verb. Similarly, *dà* and *ńkọ* constitute a type/kind/class of verb.

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“Olu went indeed”

c) Olú tiẹ̀ kúkú jẹun/sùn lánàá

“Olu indeed ate/slept yesterday”

e) Olú mà tiẹ̀ kúkú sùn lọ

“Olu even slept off indeed

“Olu even went”

d) Sẹ̀ ẹ̀ sàà jẹun?

“did you even eat (something)?

Specifically, he classified *dà*, *kẹ*, *kó*, *ńkọ*, *ni* and *wẹ* as “àpónlé aṣájú-ìṣe ajàséyìn” preverbal adverb because their meaning impact are only noticeable on elements preceding them linearly. But ‘*tiẹ̀*, *kúkú*, *ṣàà*, *ó*, *yòd/òd*, *ti*, *máa*, *ń*, etc, meaning impacts can only be marked on elements which precede or come after them. The problem becomes evident and clearer when one asks if these expressions are sentences. Yes, they are sentences because they contain predicators thereby rendering them meaningful and acceptable. The semantic impacts of *kúkú*, *tiẹ̀*, and *ṣàà* are marked on verbal items after them and not on the elements preceding them. If these examples are sentences then they are not verbless expressions.

One other feature used by Awobuluyi (2013:88) is the monosyllabic feature. He noted all verbs are monosyllabic and any defiant must have been derived in the language. As for *dà*, it is monosyllabic, whereas *ńkọ* is disyllabic. “ń” in “ńkọ” is not the progressive marker nor a form of first person single pronoun. Hence, it is indivisible. Apart from that, it was not derive from verbal compound or incorporation as:

30)	Padà	“return” ←	pa +	dà		Búra	“vow” ←	bú	ara
	Kúrò	“leave” ←	ká	iró		Pàdé	“met” ←	pa	dé

The fact that these items have certain restrictions as verbs does not render members of another other than predicates with other grammatical function in the clause.

Evidence in support of predicative functions of *dà* and *ńkọ*

In light of all the aforementioned arguments by those who argued in favour of non-predicative view of *dà* and *ńkọ*, and the shortcomings of the arguments enumerated one after the other to show that such a view is inadequate, the following are also true of the syntactic behaviour of the two interrogative items, sufficing to say that they are verbs.

- i.) **Evidence based on nominalisation with “pé”:** The complementizer, or sentence introducer as in Awobuluyi (1978), *pé* can be used to turn any clause into a noun. That is, by adjoining *pé* to clauses, and not nominal items, the result would be nominalized clauses. There is no sentence that cannot be turned into a noun through nominalization. This simply is done by attaching *pé* to the clause sentence initially. By implication, any syntactic construction that can be so turned by *pé* to a nominalised clause is a sentence in the language.

31a) mo jẹun

b) Pé mo jẹun.

I eat	that I eat
c) <i>pé mo jẹun sun ní alé àná dára</i> d)	<i>ó dára pé mo jẹun sùn ní alé àná</i>
<i>that I eat before bed last night is good</i>	<i>it is good that I eat last night</i>
e) <i>Olú rí iwin lójú àlá</i>	f) <i>Pé Olú rí iwin lójú àlá jé iró</i>
<i>Olu saw a ghost in his dreams</i>	<i>that Olu saw a ghost in his dreams is a lie</i>

In the examples above, (31a) is a simple declarative expression while (31b) is the nominalised expression with *pé*. The nominalised clause functions as the subject of the clause in (31c) and as the object in (31d). Any syntactic construction that can be so nominalised is a sentence. Similarly, example (32a) below can be nominalised as (32b), and it can be focused as in (32c).

32a) <i>Oyè dà?</i> “where is Oye?”	32b) <i>pé Oyè dà?</i> “that where is Oye?”
32c) <i>Pé Oyè dà ni ó wí</i>	32d) <i>Olú sọ pé Oyè dà?</i>
“what he said is that where is Oye?”	Olu said that where is Oye?”
32e) <i>pé Oyè dà dára</i> “that Oye is good”	

(32b) can be used as clausal complement of “sọ pé” as in (32d). The nominalised clause in (32) above shows it functions as the object of the verb *sọ*. Similarly, the nominalised clause can function as the subject of the clause.

ii.) **Evidence based on the object of the verb *şe*:** It is possible for the clause *Oyè dà* to function as the object of the verb *şe* just as the case is with focus constructions.

33) *Kíi şe Oyè dà?* “It is not ‘where is Oye?’ ”

just like every other focus expressions, e.g.

34) *Kíi şe Olú ni ó ra ajá dùgbòlugi* “It was not Olu who bought a mad dog”

iii.) **Evidence based on disjunctions (*àmó/şùgbón*) and interrogation:** These two disjunctions can only be used to link two clauses or sentences but not nominal clauses. If the clause on the right of *şùgbón/àmó* in (35) below is not a sentence as claimed by non-predicative view, then (35) should not be adjudged grammatical in the language.

35) *Mo gbà bẹ̀ẹ̀ şùgbón/àmó {Olú dà?}*

1sg agree that but/but {where is Olu} “I agree with that but {where is Olu}”

1sgE foc 1sg/HTS cont. greet Olu

3sgE foc HTS/3sg greet Olu

I am the one greeting Olu

“they are those who greeted Olu”

Examples (38a-b) above can be used as the response to (39a) below whereas (39b) cannot be so used. Based on the argument above, *dà/ńkó* cannot be classified as any other type of items other than verbs.

39a) Ta ni ó ń kí Olú?

b) *Mo/wọ̀n ni ó ń kí Olú.

Who foc HTS cont. greet Olu

“who is greeting Olu”

- v.) **Evidence based on *şé* and *ńjé*:** Every sentence can be questioned with the use of *şé/ńjé* and *bí*¹³. In the case of *dà* and *ńkó*, once the sentence are nominalised and used as subject or object of the clause, *dà/ńkó* –clause would become a subordinate clause. The derived clause can be questioned with *şé/ńjé*. Consider the following examples:

40a) Olú lọ sí ilú òkè “Olu went to the village”

b) *şé/ńjé* Olú lọ sí ilú òkè? “Did Olu go to the village?”

c) Pé Olú lọ sí ilú òkè ni orin wọ̀n “That Olu went to the village is their gossip”

d) *şé/ńjé* pé Olú lọ sí ilú òkè ni orin wọ̀n? “So, that Olu went to the village is their gossip”

e) Àwọ̀n akọ̀rin náà *dà/ńkó*? “Where are the choristers?”

f) Pé Àwọ̀n akọ̀rin náà *dà/ńkó* ni wọ̀n wí “That where are the choristers was what they said”

g) *şé* pé Àwọ̀n akọ̀rin náà *dà/ńkó* ninu wọ̀n? “So, that where are the choristers among them?”

According to Awobuluyi (1978:79) *şé* and *ńjé* are sentential adverbs attached only to sentences at the beginning of the clause to interrogate clause. Some other Yoruba scholars have used the term question marker. Apart from using *şé* and *ńjé*, *àşé* is another form of question marker which can be attached to clause to turn such clauses into interrogatives. Consider the following;

41a) Àşé pé ó lọ kò dára. “So/ I did not know that he went is good”

b) Àşé pé wọ̀n sọ pé Olú *dà* kò dára. “So/ I did not know that they said where is Olu is not good”

c) Àşé pé àwọ̀n akọ̀rin náà kò láti béèrè pé àwọ̀n omọ náà *dà/ńkó* kò dára. “So/ I did not know that that those choristers refuse to ask that where are those children is not good”

¹³ The inclusion of *bí* in this class requires a deep reflection on the behaviour of the item. This is further discussed in a separate article under preparation.

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“àšé” has a different usage which differentiate from *šé/ńjé*. It means narrowly “I did not know/realise that...” If this question marker can be used to interrogative any construction in the language then that construction in which *dà* and *ńkó* are used is a sentence predicated by *dà* or *ńkó*.

vi) Evidence based on conjunctive argument: Usually, a constituent can be tested with the use of coordination. That is, if the constituent can be coordinated, with another constituent of similar features in terms of category, phrasal or sentential quality among other things, then the said item is a constituent. In essence, a verb/verb phrase can be coordinated with a verb/verb phrase; a noun/noun phrase with a noun/noun phrase; but not a verb with a noun/NP or an adjective. Similarly, a sentence can be coordinated with a sentence if the two are have equal syntactic features otherwise coordination cannot hold. In Yoruba language, there are certain elements which have the functions of connecting or coordinating items together in phrases, clauses or/and sentences. “pèlú” and “àti” are nominal conjunctions. These conjunctions cannot be used to conjoin non-nominal elements as evident in the following examples

- 42a) *Lọlá àti Tọlá jẹ ọmọ wa*
b) *Èmi àti Bàbá mi rin irinàjò kan*
c) *Fọlá, Lọlá àti Tọlá fẹràn àbúrò wọn*
d) *Èkùn pẹlú àmọ̀tẹ̀kùn kí rin rin pọ̀*
c) *Ọkọ àti iyàwó ni wọn*
d) *Èmi pẹlú wọn fẹ sọrọ kan*
e) *Ìwọ pẹlú èmi ni wọn yàn*
f) The man and his wife want a good car

The italicized phrases are nominal phrases in which the nominal conjunctions have been used. In this regard, the italicized structures are unequivocally: [N/NP conj_(pèlú/àti)¹⁴ N/NP]. Clauses and sentences may be conjoined with “sì”, “sùgbọ̀n”, “yálà...tábí” among others in the structure [S1 conj s2];

- 43a) *Fọlá lọ sí ilú-òkè sùgbọ̀n ọ̀un dà* “Fola went the village but where is she?”
b) *Wọn ra ilẹ̀kẹ̀ sùgbọ̀n ilẹ̀kẹ̀ ọ̀un náà dà báyii* “they bought beads but where are the beads?”
c) *Bàbá fẹràn iyàwó kékéré àmọ̀ wọn kò fẹ wàhàlà rẹ̀.* “Baba loved the young wife but does not like her trouble”
d) *Ìyàwó mi ní sùgbọ̀n àmọ̀ ọ̀un náà ńkó?* “My wife has an issue but where is she exactly?”

¹⁴ “Ọ̀un” is another type often grouped with this class. It has been left out of this class following Ilori’s (2010) submission.

- e) Yàlà wòn sọ pé olú dà tàbí wòn ò sọ bèè “whether he said where is Olu or not”

If sentences containing *dà* and *ńkọ* can be conjoined just as other undisputable clauses and simple sentences with sentence conjunctions as the case is above, then such sentences are complete sentences and they have a predicator before being termed a sentence.

vii) **Referentiality argument:** Every incomplete noun phrase is referentially dependent on previously mentioned noun phrase pragmatically/semantically. Such incomplete nouns as in example (50b-c) function anaphorically by depending on another item just like pronouns.

- 44a) Àwọn ọḍe gé *eran sísun náà* sí wẹwẹ. “The hunter cut the roasted meat into small pieces”

- b) *Eran sísun náà* dà/ńkọ? “Where is that roasted meat?”

- b) *Sísun* dà/ńkọ? “Where is the roasted one?”

In examples (44b-c) *sísun* and *eran sísun náà* are both used to refer to previously mentioned items in sequential clauses. Examples (44b) and (44c) may follow logically as a sequential clause to the (44a). Hence, the addressee does not need to ask which *sísun* or *eran sísun náà* the speaker is talking about. Just like every other verbs, nominal items before *dà/ńkọ* can be referentially dependent on another nominal expression which already being mentioned in discourse.

viii) The last one is the **evidence based on subject selection**. No verb may be used in the language without either overt or covert nominal subjects. This was first noted by Awobuluyi (1978), as the following examples show.

- 45a) *Bólá àti Fólá* ra àwọn aṣọ aláráńbarà ní ojà gbági. “Bola and Fola bought some patterned clothes at Gbagi”

- b) *Wón* ra àwọn aṣọ aláráńbarà ní ojà gbági. “They bought some patterned clothes at Gbagi market”

- c) *Wón* rà wòn ní ojà gbági. “They bought them at Gbagi market”

- d) *Àwọn náà* dà/ńkọ? “Where are they?”

- 46a) *Bólá àti Fólá (náà)* dà/ńkọ? “where exactly are Bola and Fola?”

- b) àwọn aṣọ aláráńbarà náà dà? “where are the patterned clothes?”

- c) **wón* dà/ńkọ?

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In examples (45a-d), all the subjects are italicized. In (45a-c), the subject occurred in unemphatic subject position of the clause which enables the use of unemphatic pronouns to replace the subject accurately and grammatically in (45b-c). That is the position where the short unemphatic pronoun can be used. In (45d), the subject is an emphatic pronoun because of the interrogation placed on it. That suggests that movement has taken placeⁱ. And also a fact that the subject item occupies a new position i.e. a non-argument movement position termed \bar{A} - position in theoretical syntax. That position does not just allow any other type of pronoun except emphatic pronoun hence, the ungrammaticality of (46c). Invariably, *dà* and *ńkọ* select nominal subject just like every other type of verb in the language. The presence of the item “*nàà*” intensifies and emphasises the subject unlike the subject of *dà* and *ńkọ*, unlike other non-interrogative verbs in the languageⁱⁱ.

Conclusion

In summary, every syntactic category has peculiarities with which lexical items belonging to a class can be identified. In the same vein, sub-subcategories' lexical items can be identified narrowly as a member of a class as opposed to members of other class based on shared features. Lexical items may have individual notable peculiarities or features to the exclusion of items in its group that share certain number of commonalities unifying them together. If the two interrogative verbs do not behave as other verbs in the language, their syntactic properties have defined them as a class with distinctive features for characterizing them and it does not limit their predicative properties. This paper critiqued existing works on the two interrogative verbs in Yoruba. It views all the existing claims under two categories: predicative and non-predicative views. However, the paper emphasises that the two interrogative verbs are verbs in the language based on the new evidence advanced in support of predicative view. According to Bamgbose (1990), *dà/ńkọ* consists of features which make it more than just a verb. Hence, they have interrogative property unlike most verbs in the language. Pre-verbs may not occur before *dà/ńkọ* indiscriminately as argued by the paper. *dà/ńkọ* does not occur in verb serialization because it has specific function which other verbs do not have. This suffices to say that *dà* and *ńkọ* are best classified as verbs based on their predicative functions. Ignoring all these facts about the syntactic behaviour of the two interrogative verbs is tantamount to saying that the verbs do not exist at all in the language. Unless these items are not actually performing these predicative functions discussed as evidence in support of predicative interpretation and function in the Yoruba clauses, then, other interpretations may be appropriate.

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ⁱ See Taiwo and Abimbola (2014). They argued that the subject position of *dà* and *ńkó* occupies specifier position of the interrogative verb which was moved from the subject of the clause to the specifier of interrogative phrase for question to be mapped on it by the interrogative head. It was also argued in the work that *dà* and *ńkó* had moved to the head of interrogative phrase for lexicalisation.

ⁱⁱ See Ajiboye (2019) for a detail discussion on the functions of “nàà”.

List of abbreviations

NF –	non-future tense
Def-	definite
QV-	question verb
RelM-	relative marker
HTS-	high tone syllable
2sg-	second person singular pronoun
Prep.-	preposition
Obj.-	object noun phrase
1pl/1sg-	first person plural/singular pronoun
3sgE-	third person singular pronoun emphatic
Conj. -	conjunction